

THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE ON EMPLOYEES' JOB SATISFACTION

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Abstract

Organizational justice refers to the just and ethical treatment of individuals within an organization. Justice is fairness in the way that people are treated. Justice is the highest human value and precious essence in the realization of human rights. Job Satisfaction is the essential component for employee motivation and encouragement towards better performance. This study aims to explain the effect of organizational justice on job satisfaction. Further, this study analyzes the effect of organizational justice components as encompassed by three specific forms of justice perceptions; distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice on job satisfaction. This study was a descriptive correlational Research. Information gathering tools; Articles and researches with scientific validity. The Findings of study have shown that organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. As well as, organizational justice leads to employee interest in work, organizational development, and improved productivity.

Keywords: organization justice, justice, Job, Satisfaction, Employees.

1. Introduction

Organizational justice refers to justice in an organization. In the work environment, organizational justice viewed as a requirement for workers where it is used to promote the welfare and rights of workers. Organizational justice, as a key term to understanding fairness within an organizational setting, has been gradually gaining on its clarity and shape, within the time of only past few decades.

The expression of organizational justice is used in this study the degree to which employees perception about the overall organizational procedures, rules, and policies which are connected to their job should be fair while Job satisfaction means how employees has perception about their job positively or negatively. Employees were more satisfied when they felt they were fairly rewarded fairly for the work they have made and these reward are according to their contributions for organization and in harmony with reward policies of organization (Iqbal, 2013,p48). Justice is considered as one among the many values that an organization wants to promote. Employees working in organizations perceive actions or responses as Just and Unjust and it varies subjectively. Employee's attitude and behavior at work is largely affected by the judgement of what is fair? Or what is unfair? (Lind, 1997) Employees judge fairness of procedures and mechanisms, tasks, rewards and behavior towards them in the organization and they develop an attitude towards the organization in view of their judgment. according to Iqbal, (2013, p48), Justice is one of the most important factor influencing satisfactions of the personal

of an organization so that perceiving injustice will result in the personnel dissatisfaction which leave negative influence on their performance”. According to Greenberg, stated: “Organizational justice is concerned with the ways in which employees determine if they have been treated fairly in their jobs and the ways in which those determinations influence other work-related variables”. In general, there are three dimensions of organizational justice, namely: distributive justice, procedural Justice, and interactional justice. Research constantly shows that individual behavior in the workplace is affected by perception of organizational justice.

Justice keeps people together whereas Injustice can pull them apart. Justice is a main component in building up and keeping up an unwavering culture. According to Kavanagh, Brown and Benson (2007), the rise in individual productivity will result in organizational productivity. In recent times, after the advancement of science and innovation; the phenomenon of justice has taken into consideration by many researchers and various studies have been conducted to explore that how organizational justice is linked with individual’s outcomes in business world nowadays. Organization plays a crucial role for the society. Therefore, individuals considered to establish justice as one of the significant predictor of individual’s job performance (Noor-ul-Ain, 2020).

Another issue that has been raised as a variable in this article is job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is defined as the extent to which an employee feels self-motivated, content & satisfied with his/her job. Job satisfaction happens when an employee feels he or she is having job stability, career growth and a comfortable work life balance. This implies that the employee is having satisfaction at job as the work meets the expectations of the individual.

Satisfaction has a significant role in the Effectiveness and efficiency of employees ultimately plays a crucial role in the progress of an organization. As now world is like a global village so employees can move not only within country or another organization, but they can move to other countries as well. Due to high competition and efforts to access competent human resources, organizations are always in search of qualified employees and human resource is such type of asset which is most difficult to retain so organization should give concentration to those factors that can effect satisfaction of employees. In these factors organizational justice has key importance which explains how the individual perceives about the fairness of rewards he should get and what actually he receive from the organization (Fernandes & Awamleh, 2010). According of Iqbal (2013) “the organizational justice has significant impact on job satisfaction is a topic of extensively research in an organization.”

The purpose of this study is to find out the relation, rout and effect of organizational justice on job satisfaction. This research will facilitate the scholars to better understand the relationship between organization justice and job satisfaction, the effect of organizational justice on job satisfaction and employee’s performance. Also, this paper could be useful for human resource managers for formulation of HR practices which can ensure high performance trough job satisfaction by prevailing justice. Therefore, this study can be useful for researchers & managers and can also use in making more suitable strategies to increase job satisfaction of employees, and organizational productivity also, employees’ commitments.

Research method: This research is applied-basic in terms of purpose and In terms of method, descriptive research is a type of content analysis.

Information gathering tools: books, scientific articles, scientific research, etc.

2. Literature review

2.1. Organizational Justice

The notion of organizational justice is presented by Greenberg which is termed as, the employee's perception of fair treatment within the workplace. It is regards to how an employee perceive about the decision and actions taken by the organization resulting in forming employee's own behavior and attitudes towards work. Justice refers to the concept that the actions, behavior and decisions taken are ethically right. People are always concerned about the justice of events taken place every day. Individual react to these actions, behavior and decisions of the organization on daily basis. Individual's perception as unfair or fair regarding the decision of the organization can impact employees work attitudes within the workplace which will have direct impact on their productivity. In organizational settings, managers are always concerned as if their behavior and decision are perceived fairly by the employees. Owing to the fact that employee's performance and commitment could not be achieved until fairness and fair treatment prevails within the workplace. Hence justice of perception is of great importance resulting in crucial outcomes for the society and work settings. Therefore it is really important to practice fair treatment in all human practices to enhance productivity and to establish stable society especially in under developed and developing countries where there are rarely few studies on this significant phenomenon in the work settings (Noor-ul-Ain, 2020). Greenberg (1990) and Fortin (2008) cited by Yadav and Yadav, (2017) Organizational justice refers to the just and ethical treatment of individuals within an organization. Greenberg said: Organizational justice is "the term commonly used by organizational psychologists to refer to the just and fair manner in which organizations treat their employees." And also, Fortin (2008), stated: "Organizational justice helps in understanding how employees associated themselves with the complexity and multiplicity of employment relationships".

Early studies on organizational justice were directed towards two broad issues: employees' perception of what they receive (outcomes) and the process which led to these outcomes (procedures) (Behrani, 2017). Akanbi & Ofoegbu (2013) cited by Unaam, Akaninyene Okon & Benjamin, Okechukwu (2021) Organizational justice is an important factor associated with the success of every organization. In an attempt to keep employees committed to the organization, the organization needs to be fair in its system regarding organizational justice. The perception of organizational justice is thought to be an important element in ensuring the development of organizational commitment. Organizational justice covers the perceptions of the employees about the accuracy of organizational decisions and implementations, and the impact of these perceptions on the employees (Unaam, Okon & Benjamin, Okechukwu (2021). Observing justice also effect organization durability and protects its health in the long run. Observing justice is considered one of the political necessities of organizational behavior, because it enhances interest, loyalty and trust of people to the organization and adds to human

and social investment of the organizations. Williams, (2004) cited by Unaam, Akaninyene Okon & Benjamin, Okechukwu (2021) Organizational justice has the potential to create enormous benefits for organizations and employees, the benefits include more trust and commitment.

In fact, organizational justice is a term used to describe the role of fairness as it directly relates to the workplace. Specifically organizational justice is concerned with the ways in which employees are treated. If they have been treated fairly in their jobs and the ways in which those determinations influence other work-related component. Organizational justice can explain why employees retaliated against inequitable outcomes or inappropriate processes and interaction (Yaghoubi et al., 2012). Yangin and Elma, (2017) stated: "Organizational justice is not only about the gains and the distribution of these gains; it also provides the basis for the rules and their implementation and the interaction between people within an organization". Therefore, organizational justice is used to illustrate the function of fairness as it has direct effect on employee's performance, particularly organizational justice is deal with the situation when employees conclude about their treatment in their jobs and how this perception effect their work related performance. Especially, Organizational justice has the potential to create powerful benefits for organizations and employees alike.

Organizational justice is a determining factor for several organization outcomes, including job satisfaction, organizational commitment, trust, authority evaluation, Behavior, withdrawal, Negative Reaction and performance. According to Colquitt et al., 2001; Al-Zu'bi, 2010; Finch & Campbell, (2004) cited by Indahyati, Sintaasih,(2019).

Several studies concluded that the employees' feelings of being treated equally and fairly by their supervisors shall turn their attitudes into being positive. Such feelings shall positively affect those employees' behaviors and acts and promote a sense of trust within them towards the management. Such feelings shall represent an incentive that encourages those employees to cooperate with their supervisors. Such feelings shall also raise those employees' job performance level. Thus, the organization's performance levels shall increase. However, in case the employees feel that the organizational justice is absent, there shall be negative consequence. For instance, the employees' job satisfaction, commitment and job loyalty levels shall decrease. Thus, the organization's overall performance shall decrease in turn (Sulaiman Al-A'wasa, Saleh Ibrahim,2018).

2.2. Definition of organizational justice

There are many studies about term of definition of organization justice by many experts. Organizational justice can cover any issues related to perceptions of fair salary, similar opportunities to obtain promotion of career rank increase as well as appropriate selection procedure. organizational justice is center to the effects of managerial decision making, quality perception in the organization, According to tabibnia & et al., (2008),colquitt (2001) and Gibsonet et al(2012) cited by suyani and foe (2019, p, 4125). According to Greenberg & Colquitt (2005) cited by Le Roy, Bastounis and Pousard (2012), "the term of organizational

justice refers to perceptions of fairness and evaluations concerning the appropriateness of workplace outcomes or processes”.

Organizational justice is a concept that began to emerge when exploring employee satisfaction, turnover, perceptions of fairness and overall quality of the day to day experience within an organization. Organizational justice refers to the perceived fairness of the exchanges taking place in an organization, be they social or economic and involving the individual, in his or her relations with superiors, subordinates, peers; and the organization as a social system (Beugre, (1998) Cited by Kılıç, Bostan & Grabowski, (2015). Greenberg (1990) simply defined the term as employees’ perception of justice in the organization. Similarly, Moorman (1991) defined it as employees’ perception of whether they are treated fairly or not. According to Folger & Cropanzano (1998), organizational justice is the methods used for making decisions concerning distribution of organizational sources and the set of social norms and rules regulating the relations between people when these methods are applied (Terzi and et al., 2017). Finally, Organizational justice can improve attitudes and behaviors related to organizations such as commitment, trust and performance (Colquitt et al. 2001).

2.3. Justice

Throughout history, one of the basic human desires has been the implementation of justice and its realization in society. Justice is fairness in the way that people are treated. In particular, Justice is in fact, the glue that holds societies together. Justice is one of the most important moral and political concepts with no agreed definition. The word justice is derived from the latin word “jus” meaning right or law. The Oxford English Dictionary defines the “just” person as one who typically “does what is morally right” and is disposed to “giving everyone his or her due,” offering the word “fair” as a synonym. The claim for justice gains meaning in specific circumstances and cultural contexts. The evolution of the meaning of justice from the ancient Greek period to the modern day is interesting to know. One of the earliest written definitions of justice is by Aristotle. “Equals should be treated equally and unequal unequally” (Parnami,2019). According to Güriz,(1990) and Ergül, (2014) Ancient Greek philosophy defines justice as opposite meaning of injustices. In that period of time theory was that ‘people would never aware of the justice if there were not injusticesness’. Until the Aristoteles, justice was defined as love of favor in Greek philosophy. Aristoteles formed the concept of justices as whole and propounded that the term has two subcomponents as distributive justice and equilibrating justice. and Muslim clerk, philosopher and theologian, Mevlana Jalāl ad-Dīn Rumi, questioned and defined justice in 13th century as “What is justice? Giving water to trees. What is injustice? To give water to thorns. Justice consists in bestowing bounty in its proper place, not on every root that will absorb water” (Bedük, Unsacar & Kemalettin,2016).

Some scholars said: “Justice keeps people together whereas injustice can pull them apart”. Studies on justice perceptions are a critical area of research in organizational behavior because of its association with pertinent individual and organizational outcomes. Justice has been placed at the pinnacle of organizational values by Rawls (1971) when he referred to it as the "first virtue of social organizations" (Yadav and Yadav, 2017). According to Hughes, et al., (2002) cited by Iaturochmah, Sudjadi and Anggraeni,(2019) “Justice is a universal value and

becomes a human right that has been widely accepted internationally because basically everyone always wants fair treatment by the organization.” As early as 1949, Fayol, in his classic book 'General and Industrial Management' (Fayol, 1949) mentions justice when talking about “authority and responsibility”. He pointed out that “the need for sanction has its origin in a sense of justice”. Equity forms one of the 14 principles of management outlined by Fayol (1949). Reference to involving individuals to solve conflicts in organizations is a direct assertion of interactional fairness in Follett's (1949) work (Yadav and Yadav, 2017). Behind the concept of justice lies the notion of balance - that people get what is right, fair and appropriate. Accordance to Parnami, (2019), Keeping in view the various definitions of justice, it may be classified into certain kinds, namely - natural justice, economic justice social justice, political justice and legal justice. Justice is a multi-dimensional construct that evolves from how much the employees get paid to how fairly the employees are treated by upper management. Because of its content; scholars divided justice into several dimensions such as distributive justice, procedural justice and Interactional justice.

The aspect of organizational justice is very important in the life of the organization, because if justice does not exist, it can cause a decrease in commitment, the occurrence of crime in the work environment, and the desire to protest.

2.4. Dimension of organizational justice

Taxonomy, which is very popular among scholars to explain organizational justice, is distributive and procedural justice. But Bies & Moag, (1986) in their research on justice, introduced a third dimension of justice, naming it interactional justice. These three have been accepted as distinct from each other despite some correlation among them (Erdogan, 2002). Later, Greenberg (1993) contended that a four-dimension model of justice is better suited. He asserted that in addition to distributive and procedural justice, interactional justice should be divided into two separate types of justice: Interpersonal justice and informational justice. The first one is seen as the fairness of interpersonal behavior experienced during the making of procedures and distributions of outcomes, and the second one is seen as fairness in terms of explanations and information provided (Yadav and Yadav, 2017). Organizational justice consists of three dimensions, namely procedural, distributive and interactional justice. Although these three types of justice are defined in different ways based on different managerial decision, each one is interrelated with the other and constitutes the overall organizational fairness system. In the absence of any one of them, it will be difficult to develop effective organizational justice. For example, to ensure equity in distribution of employees' benefits, the decision to allocate rewards should be supported by fair procedures and accurate information.

2.4.1 Distributive Justice

Homans (1961) first proposed the concept of organizational justice as distributive justice. According to Greenberg and Baron (2008) distributive justice refers to the form of organizational justice that focuses on people's beliefs that they have received fair amounts of valued work-related outcomes for instance pay, recognition etc. distributive justice is a

perception of justice that encompasses the perceptions of the employees regarding fair distribution of resources among the members of the organization (Unaam, Akaninyene Okon & Benjamin, Okechukwu. 2021). distributive justice stated: "If rewards and other outcomes are distributed as per the established norms of the group, distributive justice has occurred". Some scholars believe that employees are likely to compare the fairness of their outcomes with those of similar employees based on their level of inputs within the organization to determine their perceptions of fairness. An employee will feel that distributive justice exists if resources are distributed equitably across employees within his or her organization relative to their inputs.

The distributive justice is defined as the perception that employees have about how the organization distributes its 'benefits' equitably. Thus, employees make a comparison of what they bring to the organization through their effort, punctuality, dedication and performance, and what they receive in return: salary, recognition in the workplace, internal promotion, etc. This analysis does not make only from an individual point of view, but also encompasses the rest of the group what they contribute and receive. The sense of injustice occurs when the expectations defined at the beginning of the relationship with the organization are not achieved, breaking the fundamental pillars of the relationship between employees and organization. In this situation, the employees consider their relationship with the organization and ask themselves the reasons why they continue in her (Castillo & Fernandez, 2017).

Alsalem & Alhaiani, (2007); Cole M., Cole. L, (1999), "Distributive justice means the perception an individual have in an organization about fairness of rewards he receives from the organization. Rewards may be distributed on the basis of equity and their work performance and individual perceives it fair in comparison with his coworker". Also that he quoted from (Gilliland, S.W, 1994), "Distributive justice is the perceived fairness of rewards. It shows how employees perceive they fairly rewarded and rewards are according to their performance". A meta-analysis examined the linkage between distributive justice and job satisfaction and concludes that very high correlation is present between these two variables. Also, study the relationship between distributive justice perceptions and pay level satisfaction and found a very high correlation between them Iqbal, (2013). According to Roch & Shanock, (2006) cited by Arif , Kundi & Khan,(2020,p49), Studies argued that procedural justice refers to fairness in procedures used in decision-making about advancement, performance appraisal, bonuses and other organizational opportunities. According to Colquitt (2001) Distributive justice is closely related to employee welfare with the intention of allocating compensation for a job that produces something material to meet the economic needs of employees. Therefore, distributive justice is a form of justice that provides a focus that employee get appropriate compensation for their work. In it there are also promotions, rewards, or rewards for employees' work and self-development. According to (Cropanzano et al., 2007) there are at least three indicators of distributive justice: first, Equity. Give rewards to employees based on the contributions they make to the company. Second, Equality. Providing equal compensation among employees. And third, Need. Provides benefits based on employee personal needs(Iaturochmah, Sudjadi, and Anggraeni,2019).

2.4.2. Procedural justice

According to (Folger & Konovsky, (1989) and Söyük, (2007), the concept of procedural justice is also referred to in the literature as "justice for implementation", "operational justice" and "process justice". Basically, procedural justice means that organizational processes are equally, honestly and fairly implemented among staff. In particular, decision making, participation in decisions, promotion and rewarding, performance appraisal, career planning, etc. (Perception of whether management is fair in activities). Procedural justice has two important elements; the first is that employees' ideas, opinion and proposals are listened and the decisions made by the employees are made easier and easier to adopt by employees, and the increased commitment of the employees as they feel they have a say in the decisions taken. The second is the style of application of policies or used by management in decision-making, resource distribution and conflict resolution (ÖKTEM and Öztoprak (2019). Procedures are seen to be fair when they encourage fair outcomes. When the individual faces outcomes that are not in consonance to his wishes or wants, here procedural justice can ease the effect of discontentment (Behrani, 2017). Also, Procedural justice shows the neutrality of the formal procedures and the rules that control a system. It has been observed that employees have perception of procedural justice if supervisors provide sufficient information about their decisions regarding procedures. Rules should show constancy of between times span and individuals in form of rewards and promotions between the employees (Iqbal, 2013).

According to Alexander and Ruderman, (1987), Stecher & Rosse and (2005) Nadiri & Tanova, (2010), Procedural Justice refers to the perceived fairness of the procedures used to make allocation decisions and distribute the outputs. Employees judge the fairness of procedures by the amount of bias, the breadth and accuracy of information gathered, number of relevant parties shared in taking decisions, ethical standards applied and the consistency and universality of decision implementation. Employees always have certain beliefs and attitudes about the way managers make and implement decisions. When the beliefs of how decisions should be made and how they are actually made are different, the employees may suffer from cognitive dissonance and they will feel uncomfortable, consequently dissatisfied (Ali Khalil and Sharaf, 2014). Leventhal et al.(1980), suggested six criteria about procedural justice, which were consistency rule, representativeness rule, bias suppression rule, accuracy rule, correctability rule and ethicality rule (Dai, L.T. and Xie, H.X,2016).

2.4.3. Interactional Justice

Interactional justice has been found to be an important variable in understanding a variety of workers attitudes and their behavior in response to layoffs, budgetary decisions, purchasing decisions, negotiating tactics, and corporate hiring practices. Moreover, interactional justice has been an important variable in understanding organizational behavior (Hernández Gracia et al., 2015). Interactional justice, which emerges as a result of managers' treatment of their employees, focuses on interpersonal communication and behaviors during the implementation of procedures (Yangin1 & Elma,2017). Interactional justice defines as the nature of association between supervisors and subordinates. The Perception of fairness affects his/her relationship with peers, subordinates and supervisors. Many workers has the perception of injustices not

due to procedural or distributive issues of rewards but they actually more concern about how actually they are treated during instead referred to the manner in which people were treated interpersonally during communication and meetings (Iqbal,2013). According to (Cropanzano et al., 2007) there are at least two indicators of interactional justice: Interpersonal Justice, Treating employees noble, polite, and Dear and Informational Justice, Share relevant information. Good between supervisor with employees or employees with follow employees(Iaturochmah, Sudjadi and Anggraeni, 2019). Interactional justices divided in to tow related parts: **Interpersonal justice** and **Informational justice** (Hernández Gracia et al. 2015). These two subcategories of informational and interactional justice overlap categories; however, research suggests that they should be considered separately, as each has differential effects on justice perceptions (Moghimi, Kazimi & samiie, 2012). A research show: Dimension of interactional justice facilitates the mechanism of external blame attribution, because the source of justice is easy to identify. Informational justice refers to the accuracy and quality of received information, whereas interpersonal justice describes the quality of interpersonal interactions, particularly those between hierarchical superiors and their subordinates (Le Roy, Bastounis and Pousard (2012).

Interpersonal justice is particularly important in shaping employee behavior. Interpersonal justice captures the degree to which people are treated properly, with dignity; politeness, and respect .Day-to-day, interpersonal encounters are so frequent in organizations that interpersonal. According to Blau, (1964) Cropanzano and Mitchell, (2005) Interpersonal justice is an important indicator of an employee's standing and value in the group, which, in turn, indicates socioemotional relevance. In contrast, low interpersonal justice likely evokes negative emotions such as sadness, frustration, and anger. These feelings are known to result in negative attitudes towards the job, poor organizational commitment, and ultimately lead to withdrawal behavior, such as higher rates of absenteeism, increased turnover intentions, and, finally, actual turnover (Leineweber et al., (2020). Interactional justice means the nature of association between supervisors and subordinates. Therefore, organizational justice is very important to the organizations because affects productivity and behavior of employees.

Interpersonal justice is concerned with the way managers treat their subordinates and the response of these subordinates, And Informational justice is concerned with the communication of information and the sufficiency of explanations given in terms of their specificity, timeliness and truthfulness. In these studies interactional justice will be treated as one construct encompassing both concepts. Perceptions of interactional justice result from the behavior of managers in building trust such as availability, competence, consistency, discreetness, fairness, integrity, loyalty, openness, promise fulfillment, receptivity and overall trust (Ali Khalil and Sharaf,2014).

Informational Justice means ‘providing knowledge about the procedures that demonstrate regards for people's concern’. This dimension measures the satisfaction with respect to the information conveyed and whether explanations were provided adequately to the employees in the outcome delivering process. It refers to whether supervisors and managers provide explanations about why certain procedures were followed or not and why certain individuals

got more or why they got less and other matters needed to be conveyed much to the satisfaction of the employees (Deepak and perwez, 2018, p545). Lee et al. (2020) described informational justice as providing correct information with integrity. Furthermore, interactional justice is viewed as more important than the other types of justice in collectivist Eastern societies (Lee, 2021, p6). Informational justice that captures employee perceptions regarding the extent to which managers explain the decisions and procedures they use.

Research has shown that employees appraise three families of workplace events. They examine the justice of outcomes (distributive justice), the justice of the formal allocation processes (procedural justice), and the justice of interpersonal transactions they encounter with others (interactional justice). These are shown in Table 1.

Table (1) Components of Organizational Justice

(1) Distributive Justice		Appropriateness of outcomes
1.1	Equity	Rewarding employees based on their contributions
1.2	Equality	Providing each employee roughly the same compensation
1.3	Need	Providing a benefit based on one's personal requirements
(2) Procedural Justice		Appropriateness of the allocation process
2.1	Consistency	All employees are treated the same
2.2	Lack of Bias	No person or group is singled out for discrimination or ill-treatment
2.3	Accuracy	Decisions are based on accurate information
2.4	Representation of All Concerned	Appropriate stakeholders have input into a decision
2.5	Correction	There is an appeals process or other mechanism for fixing Mistakes.
2.6	Ethics	Norms of professional conduct are not violated
(3) Interactional Justice		Appropriateness of the treatment one receives from authority figures
3.1	Interpersonal Justice	Treating an employee with dignity, courtesy, and respect
3.2	Informational Justice	Sharing relevant information with employees

Table (1) Components of Organizational Justice, reference: Cropanzano, Bowen & Gilliland (2007)

2.5 Job Satisfaction

Due the popularity of job satisfaction within the field of organizational psychology and organizational behavior, various scholars have provided their own definitions of what job satisfaction is. However, the two most common definitions describe job satisfaction as: “the delightful emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job as achieving or facilitating the achievement of one’s job values” and “the extent to which people like (satisfaction) or dislike (dissatisfaction) their jobs”(Sree & Satyavathi,2017). Job Satisfaction is the essential component for employee motivation and encouragement towards better performance.

Hoppock (1935) defined job satisfaction as any combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause a person truthfully to say I am satisfied with my job. According to this approach although job satisfaction is under the influence of many external factors, it remains something internal that has to do with the way how the employee feels. That is job satisfaction presents a set of factors that cause a feeling of satisfaction (Azizi, 2011). In general, most definitions cover the affective feeling an employee has towards their job. This could be the job in general or their attitudes towards specific aspects of it, such as:

their colleagues, pay or working conditions. However, Job satisfaction is not just about employee satisfaction with work, but also about job satisfaction, productivity, greater commitment, and better and more effective learning.

According to Armstrong, (2006) “The term job satisfaction refers to the attitude and feelings people have about their work. Positive and favorable attitudes towards the job indicate job satisfaction. Negative and unfavorable attitudes towards the job indicate job dissatisfaction” According to a series of studies, job satisfaction often causes life satisfaction and life satisfaction is a key factor in progress and development. According to Beharani, (2017), There is a close relationship between job and life satisfaction. Job satisfaction affects life satisfaction while life satisfaction also affects job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction is one of the most comprehensively measured and researched topics in the fields of management and organizational psychology. Job satisfaction has been defined as the connection between what one expects from job and what his perception about getting from job. Job satisfaction is taken seriously based on the assumption that higher job satisfaction lead to higher work performance.

In otherworld, Job satisfaction has been defined and measured both as a global construct and as a concept with multiple dimensions or facts. In general, overall job satisfaction has been defined as “a function of the perceived relationship between what one wants from one’s job and what one perceives it as offering”. Job satisfaction is an attitude that people have about their jobs and the organizations in which they perform these jobs (Yaghoubi, 2012).

Existence of job satisfaction is very important in an organization as it has significant impact in many fields like human resource management, organizational behavior, Productivity, sociology, and strategic management etc. That why job satisfaction should exists wherever jobs occur. Employees received reward not only in the form of salary again their performance but can also be in the form of sense of achievement or feelings of internal satisfaction. Research of Al-Zubi (2010) shows that employees with job satisfaction have positive effect on work which shows the presence justice in the organization. Job satisfaction is very important in retaining and catching the attention of capable personnel. Job satisfaction is a perception of employees about their duties and the organizations in which they work. Job satisfaction as an employee’s feedback to his work, on the basis of comparison between desired rewards and actual rewards (Iqbal, 2013). Also, Job satisfaction represents one of the most complex areas facing today’s managers when it comes to managing their employees. Many studies have demonstrated an unusually large impact on the job satisfaction on the motivation of workers, while the level of motivation has an impact on productivity, and hence also on performance of business organizations. Unfortunately, in our country, job satisfaction has not still received the proper attention from neither scholars nor managers of various business organizations.

Job satisfaction is one of the most researched variables in the area of workplace psychology, and has been associated with numerous psychosocial issues ranging from leadership to job design. Job satisfaction is related to the psychology of an employee. A happy & content employee at a job is always motivated to contribute more. On the other hand, a dissatisfied

employee is lethargic, makes mistakes & becomes a burden to the organization. In fact, job satisfaction is the feeling of success and achievement of the worker at work. It is generally thought to be directly related to productivity as well as personal well-being.

According to (Kivimaki & Kalimo, (1994) Schermerhorn et al, (2005) Yang, Brown, & Byongook Moon, (2011) Deferent Scientific research's, have been shown: more satisfied employees exhibit loyalty, innovative attitude for continuous betterment and show more involvement in the decision origination process in the best interest of the organizations goals. Job satisfaction is also quite correlated to customer's satisfaction. As job satisfaction has great impact on attitudes and behavior of employees and productivity. For many years, researchers illustrate how satisfaction effect and is effected by other organizational variables. Individual personality, job characteristics, disposition were detected as the major predictor of job satisfaction. Also, Positive and caring relationships with coworkers also have a positive impact on job satisfaction of employees. An individual that has a better relationship with their coworkers are more likely to be satisfied with their job (Iqbal, 2013). Another study show (Bigliardi, Dormio, Galati, & Schiuma, 2012) Job satisfaction expresses itself in different ways in different people; its intensity depends on many factors like working environment, person's needs, expectations and individual personality. According of Karim & Rehman (2012), in brief, the degree of happiness of an employee has toward the job is called job satisfaction. Job satisfaction further implies enthusiasm and happiness with one's work. When analyzing job satisfaction the logic that a satisfied employee is a happy employee and a happy employee is a successful employee (Aziri, 2011). Many studies have related employee's satisfaction with their jobs in general particularly with fairness, and have linked organizational justice to job satisfaction. Employees tend to have a good perception of organizational justice when they are satisfied (Krishnan, 2020). Job satisfaction is generally encompasses certain dimensions of satisfaction related to work environment, benefits, pay, relationship with peers, promotion opportunities and administration.

According to Landy (1978) cited by Abuhashesh, et. al, 2019) Influencing factors are on job satisfaction; payment, working hours, schedule, benefits, level of stress, and flexibility. Job satisfaction has been linked to productivity, motivation, performance, and life satisfaction. According to Ahmad et al. (2012) and Valaei and Rezaei (2016), most of the scholar generally pay attention to the two most used determinants of job satisfaction which are demographic variables and work environment variables. In this study, the scholar focused on the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance by using job satisfaction survey by Spector (1994) which covers nine job satisfaction dimensions as pay, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, co-workers, nature of work and communication. These nine dimensions are necessary for determining job satisfaction (Ratia and Tuzlukaya, 2019).

In a research Spector (1994) which stated nine job satisfaction dimensions, these dimension includes: as pay, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, co-workers, nature of work and communication. These nine dimensions are necessary for determining job satisfaction (Ratia and Tuzlukayab,2019).

Ostrom and Lacobucci (1995) defined satisfaction as the emotional and cognitive state of perceiving that one has been appropriately rewarded for the cost paid. (Yoo & Park, 2020) stated its cognitive aspect by conceptualizing satisfaction as customers' assessment of the expectation before consumption and perceived performance after consumption. Taken together, satisfaction is a cognitive and affective emotion felt by customers relating to the performance of a product and service (Lee, 2021). In fact, job satisfaction as a result of employee perceptions of how well their work provides things that are considered important (Ratnasari et al 2020).

Job satisfaction is a positive attitude and behavior at workplaces and influence employees to commit with their job requirement. According to Harter et al, (2002); Liao & Chang, (2004) and (Ellinger et al, 2003), Employees' satisfaction indicates the happy and contented employees as they can fulfil their own desires and requirements through their jobs. Employee satisfaction leads towards their motivation and high morale to perform well enough to achieve the organizational goals. If organizational goals are aligned with the employees' personal goals than employees feel happier and contented towards their jobs and organizations. Thus, organizations are required to align the organizational goals in terms of employees' personal goal achievement as their satisfaction will lead them to enhance their contribution towards organizational goal achievement. Employee satisfaction can also be gained through treating them with respect, providing them with recognition in the organization, offering benefits beyond industry averages, offering employee perks and empowering them. These factors will contribute well in attaining employee satisfaction that will engage them more towards their work and ultimately improving their contribution towards goal attainment (Dahkoul, 2018). Job satisfaction is the favorableness with which employees view their work.

Mueller & Kim (2008) identified two types of job satisfaction; firstly, the overall feeling about the job, and secondly, the feelings about the aspects of the job, such as benefits, salary, position, growth opportunities, work environment, and the relationships among employees. The considerable time spent by employees at the work place makes job satisfaction a significant factor since dissatisfaction can have an adverse impact on the individual's personal life (Abuhashesh, et al, 2019). Job satisfaction is an affective or emotional response to various aspects of one's work.

According to Dahqvist and Matsson (2013), the job satisfaction and job dissatisfaction influence the employee performance. Job satisfaction is increased by intrinsic motivational factors such as advancement, achievement, work itself, recognition and growth. Factors, which decrease job dissatisfaction, are organizational policy, good working conditions, job security, supervision, relationship with peers and money. Job satisfaction increase the employee's satisfaction and job dissatisfaction decrease the employee's satisfaction that ultimately give results in poor performance (shaikh et al., 2019).

Employees' feeling of dissatisfaction reflects the decision of leaving the organization. For example, if there is unfairness in the pay of salaries, limited growth opportunity, etc. Lack of benefits and trust by employers to employees will initiate dissatisfaction and in turn contribute to employees' turnover. In contrast, dissatisfaction effects organization in negative ways.

Dissatisfaction in turn will lead to stress, which drives employees' feeling of unhappiness with their job. According to Branham (2005) found 25% to 50% workers feel some level of dysfunction due to stress. As a result to this feeling, employees attitudes suggest negative effects, such low productivity and quitting the organization. The causes of stress may come from lack of facilities, equipment and tools to produce or work efficiently on the job. All these resulted in lower productivity and higher turnover. In this sense, employers are more concern to the revenue, profit and productivity rather than employees' wellbeing who are working for them. This will definitely lead to job dissatisfaction and resulted in employees to resign and jumping to other organization that offer better benefit and advantages. Another cause is lack in communication at workplaces; contribute to high rate of job dissatisfaction (Munir, and Ramlee,2016).

2.6 Relation between OJ & JS

The relationship between job satisfaction and employees' performance has been a topic of interest for researchers for a very long time. The relationship between justice perceptions and job satisfaction is well established in Western literature (e.g., Bakhshi, Kumar, & Rani, 2009; Bhupatkar, 2003; Fatt, Khin, & Heng, 2010; Malik & Naeem, 2011; Nojani, Arjmandnia, Afrooz, & Rajabi, 2012; Schappe, 1998; Schmiesing, Safrit, & Gliem, 2003). For example, Schappe (1998), Colquitt et al. (2001), and Bakhshi et al. (2009), stated that distributive justice was an important predictor of job satisfaction. Furthermore, Masterson et al. (2000) found procedural justice to be a stronger predictor of job satisfaction than interactional justice. The findings of Zainalipour et al. (2010), study showed significant positive relationships between job satisfaction and organizational justice. They stated: Distributive justice and interactional justice positively correlated with four facets of job satisfaction namely; supervision, coworker, pay and promotion and they did not have correlation with nature of job as a facet of job satisfaction.

In a non-western context, Al-Zu'bi (2010) investigated the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction in Jordan industrial companies. He found a significant positive correlation between employees' satisfaction and all dimensions of organizational justice (i.e., distributive, procedural and interactional justice). Elamin and Alomaim (2011) studied the effects of organizational justice perceptions on job satisfaction, and self-perceived performance in Saudi Arabia. They found that perceptions of organizational justice affect job satisfaction for both Saudi and non-Saudi employees (Altahayneh, Khasawneh, & Abedalhafiz,2017). Garrin (2014) and Musyoka (2015) mentioned that job satisfaction leads to higher productivity, organizational responsibility and employees' physical and mental health which in turn increases performance. When workers are highly pleased with their jobs they work hard, they meet deadlines and submit high-quality work. This is also influenced by loving what they do, this means that satisfaction leads to high job performance and dedication ((Ratia and Tuzlukaya, 2019). A study conducted by Afridi and Baluch in (2018) about the effect of organizational justice on job satisfaction has clearly achieved the following results: "The results of this study show that the components of organizational justice (distributive justice and procedural justice) has a positive and a significant relationship with job satisfaction, results also indicates that

distributive justice and procedural justice both are predictors of job satisfaction. Result shows a positive and significant relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction and is a predictor of organizational justice.”

3 CONCLUSIONS

This paper reports the basic findings of a study that investigated the effects of organizational justice on job satisfaction and also defined the relationship between dimensions of organizational justice and another related terms which that effect on organizational justice and employees’ jobs satisfaction. The main purpose of this study was to determine the effect of organizational justice on job satisfaction, significant relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction, employees’ performance.

The paper involves two variables, namely organizational justice and job satisfaction. Both of them necessary for each other’s. The first one is organizational justice and the second one is job satisfaction. Organizational justice is “the term commonly used by organizational psychologists to refer to the just and fair manner in which organizations treat their employees.” Organizational justice is classified differently by various researchers. Some ones classified it into procedural and distributive justice; while Greenberg (1990) classified it as distributive, procedural, and interactional justice. Distributive justice reflects the perceived fairness, with regard to how resources and rewards are distributed, and allocated in organizations. Procedural justice is defined as the perceived fairness of the process and procedures, used to make allocation decisions. Interactional justice relates to the “quality of the interpersonal treatment people receive, when procedures are implemented.” However, scholars today divide interactional justice into interpersonal justice and informational justice. As an above of mentioned, organizational justice consists of three dimensions, namely procedural, distributive and instructional justice. These dimensions of justice are defined in different ways based on different managerial decision; each one is interrelated with the other and constitutes the overall organizational fairness system. It is very important that in the absence of any one of them, it will be difficult to develop effective organizational justice and good employees’ performance.

Job satisfaction as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job or job experiences. Or Job satisfaction as combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental circumstances that cause a person to truthfully say that they are satisfied from job. Job satisfaction represents one of the most complex areas facing today’s managers when it comes to managing their employees. Many studies have demonstrated an unusually large impact on the job satisfaction on the motivation of workers, while the level of motivation has an impact on productivity, and hence also on performance of business organizations. Organizational justice is a determining factor for several organization productivity such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, trust, authority evaluation, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, withdrawal, Negative Reaction and performance, and also some scholars found the positive relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction.

Findings of this paper tell that there was positive significant relationship between distributive justice and employees of job satisfaction. Also, there was significant relationship between

procedural justice and job satisfaction. Further, Interactional justice has a significant effect on job satisfaction. Also, several studies have been undertaken by past researchers to understand the issue of fairness in the workplace. As well as, the Findings of this study have shown that organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. As well as, organizational justice leads to employee interest in work, organizational development, and improved productivity. Further, the results of this study show that the components of organizational justice (distributive justice, procedural and interactional justice) has a significant effect on job satisfaction, results also indicates that organizational justice dimensions are predictors of job satisfaction. Job satisfaction leads to higher productivity, organizational responsibility and employees' physical and mental health which in turn increases performance. Also, organizational justice coordinates employees, but injustice makes employees hate and disperse in the organization.

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